

The concept of an arms trade treaty **10 November 2009**

The right of states to participate in a legitimate trade in arms is derived from and counter-balanced by their responsibility to protect citizens, including the responsibility to provide assistance to victims of armed violence. A treaty that affirms the right of states to participate in a legitimate trade in arms should only be supported if it also strongly articulates the responsibilities of states towards victims of armed violence.

The trade in arms may be legitimate if bounded by precautionary obligations to ensure against, *inter alia*, transfers that may facilitate violations of international humanitarian law or international human rights law or that may fuel persistent patterns of armed violence (whether in the form of conflict or crime).

The right of states to engage in this trade is justified by their acceptance of corollary responsibilities to protect citizens and support the full realisation of citizen's rights, and must not be de-coupled from these responsibilities. Specifically, a legal instrument affirming the right of states to engage in a legitimate trade in arms should delineate the responsibility of states to measure the impact of armed violence and to assist the victims of armed violence (in addition to requiring other policy and programmatic measures towards armed violence reduction).

These provisions, already established in certain international legal instruments, should recognise that victims of armed violence means all persons who have been killed or suffered physical or psychological injury, economic loss, social marginalisation or substantial impairment of the realisation of their rights caused as a result of armed violence - including those persons directly impacted as well as their families and affected communities.

Each state, with respect to victims of armed violence in areas under its jurisdiction or control shall, in accordance with applicable international humanitarian and human rights law, adequately provide age-, gender- and community- sensitive assistance, including medical care, rehabilitation and psychological support, as well as provide for their social and economic inclusion. Each state shall ensure collection of, and publically report, reliable relevant data with respect to victims of armed violence.

Through international cooperation and assistance states shall support each other towards the full implementation of these obligations.

The responsibility to document the impact of armed violence is a necessary corollary of the precautionary rules by which states must judge whether arms transfers would be legal or not.

Whilst it might be argued that some victims of armed violence are also perpetrators, this does not abrogate their rights.

These obligations towards the victims of armed violence are supported by existing non-discriminatory obligations accepted by states in international human rights law and international humanitarian law, including *inter alia* the Mine Ban Treaty, The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, the Convention on Cluster Munitions and the politically binding Plan of Action on Victim Assistance under Protocol V of the UN Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons.